

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SYSTEM OF BUSINESS AND EDUCATION INTERACTION: THE CHINESE EXPERIENCE

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Abstract

In the context of the digital transformation of the global economy, the interaction between business and the education system is becoming strategically important for the development of human capital and digital competencies. The purpose of this study is to analyze the Chinese experience in implementing digital technologies in business education and the corporate sector, as well as to identify the possibilities for its adaptation in Kazakhstan.

The methodological basis of the study includes the Triple Helix concept, the theory of digital transformation in education, and the ecosystem approach. The research employs comparative analysis, case study analysis, content analysis, and a systems approach.

The results of the study demonstrate that the Chinese model is characterized by a high level of digitalization, active use of LMS, ERP, CRM, Big Data, and AI technologies, as well as close integration between universities and the corporate sector.

It has been established that the adaptation of the Chinese experience can contribute to the development of digital business education, corporate training, and university–business partnerships in Kazakhstan.

The information base of the study includes scientific publications, official university websites, analytical materials, and international studies in the field of digital education and corporate training.

Keywords: digitalization, business education, corporate sector, digital platforms, China, university – business interaction.

Introduction. The development of the digital economy has a significant impact on the system of higher and business education. In the context of digitalization, labor market requirements, approaches to personnel training, and mechanisms of interaction between educational institutions and the corporate sector are changing. Modern companies require specialists with digital competencies, skills in working with information systems, and the ability to adapt to rapidly changing conditions of the digital environment.

Under these conditions, the interaction between business and education becomes particularly relevant. The integration of universities and the corporate sector contributes to the development of practical competencies, the formation of an innovative environment, and the improvement of human capital competitiveness.

China is one of the global leaders in the field of digital transformation in education. Chinese business schools actively implement digital platforms, artificial intelligence technologies, Big Data, and corporate learning systems. In addition, China has developed an effective model of interaction between universities and business focused on practice-oriented learning and the development of digital competencies.

In Kazakhstan, the processes of digitalization in business education are also developing actively; however, the level of integration between educational institutions and business remains insufficient. In this regard,

the study of the Chinese experience is of considerable scientific and practical interest.

Research Question and Hypothesis. How can the Chinese model of digital integration between business education and the corporate sector be adapted to the conditions of Kazakhstan’s higher education system?

The integration of digital platforms, corporate training systems, and partnership relations between universities and business, based on the Chinese experience, can improve the effectiveness of business education and the development of digital competencies in Kazakhstan.

Literature Review. The issues of digitalization in education and the interaction between business and universities are actively studied in contemporary scientific literature. Many researchers note that digital transformation affects not only economic processes but also personnel training mechanisms.

The Fourth Industrial Revolution creates new requirements for professional competencies and accelerates the implementation of digital technologies in the educational environment. In his research, Schwab K. emphasizes the importance of developing flexible educational models and lifelong learning [1].

The issues of university–business integration are considered within the framework of the Triple Helix concept proposed by H. Etzkowitz and L. Leydesdorff.

The authors emphasize that interaction between universities, business, and government is a key factor in the innovative development of the economy [2].

A significant contribution to the development of this concept was made by Y. Cai and H. Etzkowitz in the article “*Theorizing the Triple Helix model: Past, present, and future.*” The authors consider the Triple Helix as a theoretical and practical foundation for the formation of an innovation economy and digital ecosystems.

The researchers emphasize that interaction between universities, business, and government is becoming a key factor in innovative and technological development. Under modern conditions, universities increasingly perform entrepreneurial functions, business participates in educational processes, and the government creates institutional conditions for digital transformation.

Particular attention is paid to the impact of digitalization on the development of the Triple Helix model. According to Cai and Etzkowitz, digital platforms, Big Data, and artificial intelligence strengthen the integration of the educational environment and the corporate sector by creating new mechanisms for knowledge exchange and innovation.

The authors also note that the Triple Helix model can be effectively applied to the analysis of interaction between business education and the corporate sector. In the context of the digital economy, this concept allows the study of digital educational ecosystems, corporate training, and university–business partnerships [3].

Studies by Huang et al. show that Chinese universities actively use artificial intelligence technologies and Big Data in educational systems. The authors note that digital platforms improve learning management efficiency and provide flexibility in the educational process [4].

Li et al. analyze the processes of digital transformation in Chinese business education and conclude that the use of ERP, CRM, and LMS systems contributes to the development of students’ practical managerial skills [5].

Despite the significant number of studies, the issues of adapting the Chinese experience of digitalization in business education to Kazakhstan remain insufficiently explored. In particular, the mechanisms of integration between universities and the corporate sector in the context of the digital economy have received limited attention. Kazakhstani researchers mainly focus on individual aspects of educational digitalization, e-learning, and the development of digital infrastructure [6–9].

At the same time, the issues of integration between business education and the corporate sector in the context of digitalization, especially from the perspective of adapting the Chinese experience, remain insufficiently studied. Unlike existing studies focusing on отдельные aspects of educational digitalization, this article examines a comprehensive model of interaction between business education and the corporate sector based on the adaptation of the Chinese experience to the conditions of Kazakhstan. Despite the growing number of studies on digital education, limited attention has been

paid to adapting Chinese university–business integration models to Kazakhstan’s business education system.

Research Methodology. The methodological framework of the study is based on the Triple Helix concept, the theory of digital transformation in education, and the ecosystem approach. To increase the reliability of the results, scientific publications, analytical materials, and practical cases of Chinese business schools were comparatively analyzed.

In the context of the formation of the digital economy, the business education system is undergoing significant changes. The development of digital technologies, automation of business processes, and growth of data volumes create new requirements for personnel training and interaction between educational institutions and the corporate sector. The modern labor market requires specialists possessing digital competencies, information system skills, and the ability to adapt to rapidly changing conditions of the digital environment.

The object of the study is Chinese business schools implementing digital models of business education and corporate training. The subject of the study is the mechanisms of digital interaction between universities and the corporate sector under conditions of economic digital transformation.

Chinese business schools actively implement digital education models.

To study the mechanisms of digital interaction between business and education, the practices of leading Chinese business schools actively implementing digital technologies and corporate learning models were examined. The analysis showed that the Chinese business education system is characterized by a high degree of integration between universities and the corporate sector, as well as extensive use of digital platforms and analytical systems.

One of the most representative examples is the China Europe International Business School (CEIBS), which is considered one of the leading business schools in Asia. CEIBS actively uses digital educational technologies, online learning systems, and artificial intelligence-based analytical tools. An important feature of the school is its close cooperation with international corporations and its focus on practice-oriented learning. Corporate projects, internships, and business participation in the educational process allow students to develop modern managerial and digital competencies. In addition, CEIBS actively develops executive education programs aimed at improving managerial qualifications in the context of the digital economy [10].

The experience of the School of Management of Fudan University is also of significant interest. The university actively implements Big Data technologies, digital analytical platforms, and educational management systems. A key feature is the cooperation of the business school with Chinese technology companies and the integration of ERP, CRM, and business analytics into management education. The use of digital platforms provides flexibility in the educational process and contributes to the development of an innovative educational environment [11].

Another successful example is the Antai College of Economics and Management at Shanghai Jiao Tong University. The college implements a strategy of digital transformation in education and actively cooperates with the corporate sector. Particular attention is paid to the development of online learning systems, corporate educational programs, and digital platforms for executive education. Cooperation with Chinese and international companies allows the integration of practical business cases into the educational process and improves the quality of specialist training [12].

The conducted analysis shows that the common features of Chinese business schools include a high level of digitalization, close integration with the corpo-

rate sector, the development of practice-oriented learning, and the use of digital platforms in educational management processes. This experience is of practical interest for Kazakhstan in the context of modernizing business education and developing university–business partnerships.

Digitalization has a comprehensive impact on the business education system. Traditional educational models are gradually transforming into flexible digital ecosystems based on the use of online platforms, cloud technologies, artificial intelligence, and analytical tools. In this regard, EdTech and Smart Education, aimed at integrating technologies into the educational process, are becoming particularly important.

Table 1

Comparative Characteristics of Business Education Models in China and Kazakhstan

Criteria	Kazakhstan	China
Level of digitalization	Medium	High
Use of LMS	Partial	Extensive
ERP/CRM training	Limited	Integrated
Practice orientation	Medium	High
Corporate partnership	Limited	Systematic
AI and Big Data	Low level	Active implementation

Source: Compiled by the author.

According to Table 1, the Chinese model is characterized by a higher level of digital integration and a closer connection between educational programs and business needs. In Kazakhstan, digitalization is developing less systematically, which limits the effectiveness of interaction between business and the educational environment.

Modern models of interaction between business and education are aimed at developing practical competencies and integrating the educational process with

the requirements of the corporate sector. The most common models include dual education, corporate universities, and industrial partnerships.

Dual education combines theoretical training with practical activities at enterprises. Corporate universities are established by large companies for continuous staff training and the development of digital competencies. Industrial partnerships involve the joint participation of universities and business in educational and research projects.

Table 2

Elements of the corporate training system

Element	Content	Result
Corporate training programs	Professional development	Competency growth
Online learning	LMS and digital courses	Learning flexibility
Practical case studies	Solving business problems	Practical skills
Internships	Work in companies	Adaptation to the labor market
Reskilling/Upskilling	Acquisition of new skills	Human capital development

Source: Compiled by the author.

Modern corporate training models are focused on the continuous development of personnel and adaptation to the conditions of the digital economy. These mechanisms are especially actively used in the Chinese business education system.

The presented model (Figure 1) reflects the integration of the educational environment, digital platforms, and the corporate sector into a unified personnel training system.

The Chinese business education system is characterized by a high level of digitalization and practical orientation. Chinese business schools actively implement digital platforms, artificial intelligence technologies, and analytical learning management systems.

Figure 1. Model of Digital Integration Between Business and Education

Source: Compiled by the author.

LMS platforms, cloud technologies, and Big Data tools are widely used in the educational environment. The use of AI makes it possible to automate knowledge

assessment, analyze student behavior, and create individualized learning trajectories.

Table 3

Characteristics of Digital Platforms in Business Education

Platform	Purpose	Advantages
LMS	Online learning	Flexibility and accessibility
ERP	Resource management	Practical skills
CRM	Customer process management	Preparation for the business environment
BI systems	Data analytics	Decision-making support
Cloud systems	Data storage	Process integration

Source: Compiled by the author.

The data presented in Table 3 show that digital platforms play a key role in the transformation of modern business education. The use of LMS, ERP, and CRM systems contributes to the development of practical skills, increases learning flexibility, and integrates the educational process with the needs of the corporate sector.

BI systems and cloud technologies are of particular importance as they provide analytical support, data processing, and effective management of educational processes. The analysis demonstrates that the implementation of digital platforms improves the quality of specialist training and contributes to the development of digital competencies in the context of the digital economy.

A key feature of the Chinese model is the close integration between universities and business. Corpo-

rate partners participate in the development of educational programs, organization of internships, and implementation of research projects.

Practice-oriented learning allows students to gain professional experience during the educational process. Large Chinese companies establish corporate universities and digital platforms for continuous learning.

Figure 2 reflects the mechanism of interaction between universities and the corporate sector in the context of the digital economy. The model demonstrates the interconnection between educational programs, joint projects, internships, and corporate training aimed at developing practical and digital competencies. Feedback from the business sector plays a particularly important role in this system, ensuring the adaptation of educational programs to labor market requirements.

Figure 2. University-Business Interaction Mechanism

Source: Compiled by the author [2,3].

In the Chinese educational system, digital platforms are used not only for organizing the learning process but also for integrating business and education into a unified digital ecosystem.

ERP and CRM systems are applied for educational purposes to model business processes and develop

managerial skills. Online learning systems provide distance education and access to educational resources.

Digital analytics plays a particularly important role. BI systems and Big Data technologies make it possible to analyze learning outcomes, forecast labor market needs, and improve the quality of managerial decision-making.

Figure 3. Digital Ecosystem Scheme of Business Education

Source: Compiled by the author [2,3].

Figure 3 reflects the structure of the digital ecosystem of business education in the context of the digital economy. The model demonstrates the interconnection between artificial intelligence, Big Data, cloud technologies, and digital platforms (LMS, ERP, CRM, BI systems) in the process of interaction between universities and the corporate sector.

Digital platforms play a particularly important role in this system by ensuring the integration of the educational process, corporate training, and analytical management mechanisms. As a result, a modern human capital development system is formed, aimed at developing digital competencies, innovative thinking, and practical skills.

Conclusion and Recommendations. The conducted study demonstrated that digitalization significantly transforms the system of interaction between business and education, creating new requirements for personnel training and the development of digital competencies. It was established that the Chinese business education model is characterized by a high level of integration between universities and the corporate sector, active use of LMS, ERP, CRM, Big Data, and AI technologies, as well as practice-oriented learning.

The study included an analysis of scientific literature, a comparative study of business education models in China and Kazakhstan, and a case analysis of CEIBS, Fudan University, and Antai College. The comparative analysis was conducted according to the criteria of the level of digitalization, the use of digital platforms, the degree of university–business integration, the development of corporate training, and the application of AI and Big Data technologies.

The results of the study showed that Kazakhstan still faces problems related to insufficient integration between business and universities, limited use of digital technologies, and inadequate development of practical competencies. As practical recommendations, the study proposes the development of university–business partnerships, the implementation of corporate training programs, and the expansion of digital platforms in the educational environment.

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